

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D9.5

Report on Training Events Y2

WP 9 – T9.4

Partnership
for the
Assessment
of
Risks
from
Chemicals

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¹ PU = Public

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Abstract

This deliverable provides an overview of training held under PARC Task 9.4 from M13 (June 2023) to M30 (October 2024). PARC 1st training plan, which was built on training needs identified by partners and stakeholders, has been successfully implemented so far, with three in-person courses completed according to schedule. Attendance and feedback indicate that the training plan has been well received, with participants expressing a high level of satisfaction. The development of online resources is slightly delayed, but it will align with the training library currently under development that will compile both internal and external training materials. In addition to the main training program, several internal training initiatives have been conducted within the consortium, that primarily consist of webinars and workshops tailored to specific topics relevant to PARC tasks and projects.

Overall, the task progress has been very positive, with significant achievements. However, several challenges and areas for improvement have been identified. Task 9.4 partners remain dedicated to addressing these issues and overcoming obstacles that will contribute to building and enhancing interdisciplinary research capacities among stakeholders and partners.

Key Words

Capacity-building; training needs; training plan; staff exchange; online resources

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Acronyms

3PFF: 3 Point Fairification Framework

AD: Additional Deliverable

D: Deliverable

FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable

FAQ: Frequently Asked Questions

PARC: Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

SOP: Standard Operation Procedure

SYNET: PARC network for collaboration and knowledge sharing

WP: Work Package

1. Introduction

Task 9.4 (*Training*) of WP9 (*Building infrastructural and human capacities*) aims to build and strengthen the interdisciplinary research capacity of stakeholders and partners. This will include promoting knowledge acquisition and exchange, contributing to skills development, and increasing capacities to apply new tools and methodologies developed in PARC. Additionally, this task aims to contribute to stakeholders' and partners' preparedness to address current and new challenges in the field of chemical risk assessment.

The task's main activities include (1) the identification of partners' and stakeholders' training needs; (2) the mapping of existing training courses and resources, and (3) the definition of a flexible and dynamic training plan aligned with the identified needs, as well as with PARC progress and findings.

In the first year of PARC, with the application of the online survey to PARC partners and stakeholders, it was possible to collect a broad input on possible training topics, their importance, and preferred target audience, difficulty level, and delivery format, as previously detailed in D9.3. This data has provided ground for subsequent task activities that include the mapping of the available training courses and resources, and the definition of a comprehensive training plan (covering October 2023 to October 2025), detailed in AD9.1. This training plan included both the organization of training courses (in person and remote) and open access online resources development, as presented below in **Figure 1**. In parallel, Task 9.4 outlined a staff exchange procedure (for on-the-job training), to promote an efficient and effective transfer of skills and knowledge among project partners.

Figure 1. PARC 1st Training plan (October 2023 to Oct 2025), as submitted in AD9.1

The present deliverable (D9.5) details all the training initiatives held under Task 9.4 of PARC from M13 (June 2023) to M30 (October 2024), that include training courses ([section 2.1](#)), online resources ([section 2.2](#)), staff exchange ([section 2.3](#)), mapping existing training ([section 2.4](#)), as well as all deviations from the initially planned (include add-ins and delays). In [section 2.5](#), this document lists also training initiatives held under other tasks of PARC.

2. Training Activities

As mentioned above, planned training activities include (1) in-person courses, that provide a more engaging and effective learning experience, in which participants have the chance to receive immediate feedback and collaborate with their peers; (2) remote courses, that promote inclusiveness by providing high quality information to a global audience; (3) online resources, to allow self-paced learning for users' convenience, and finally, (4) staff exchange, to provide researchers with a unique opportunity to improve their skills and knowledge by working daily hand in hand with experts in a real context.

Since the submission of AD9.1 in early 2024, PARC 1st training plan has undergone several updates, including the addition of new training courses, such as 2nd SSbD Bootcamp (in person) and a remote course on proficiency testing and reference materials (GCSL, EL). In terms of online resources, the plan now also includes a slide deck on non-targeted screening, to be developed by BPI, EL, and a slide deck on Basic Toxicology, contributed by UEF, FI. These additions aim to broaden the training plan scope and ensure that it addresses emerging needs within the field, providing more comprehensive and accessible learning resources for all partners and stakeholders. The current version of PARC 1st Training plan is provided below in **Figure 2**.

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Figure 2. PARC 1st Training plan (Nov 2023 to Oct 2025); updated by 08.11.2024

2.1. Training courses

2.1.1. Overview

In accordance with the PARC 1st Training plan published in AD9.1, up to M30 of PARC two in-person training courses were held, namely the *FAIR Data and Databases* course, and the *Chemical Exposure and Modelling* course. In addition to these, the 2nd SSbD Bootcamp was also organised under PARC, in collaboration with Task 9.4, and therefore added to the PARC 1st Training plan.

Up to M30, a fourth in-person training course has also been announced: the *Health Risk Assessment of Chemicals – principles and applications* course that will be held in November 2024 under the coordination of IMM-KI. Details of this course will be presented in the next training report.

The organisation of these training courses within PARC has required close communication among Task 9.4 co-leaders, project partners, scientific course coordinators, and Task 3.2. The workflow, from initial setup to course delivery and satisfaction evaluation, is presented in [Annex 1](#).

To note that one of the goals established in AD9.1 was that all PARC training would be made open and free (no registrations fees will apply) to PARC members and non-members to ensure inclusiveness, and in fact, all the courses listed under section 2.1.2 followed this rule.

2.1.2. Courses held (in-person)

Detailed information on courses held under PARC Task 9.4 is provided in sections 2.1.2.1, 2.1.2.2, and 2.1.2.3, while a short summary of indicators is provided below in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Main indicators of in-person courses held under PARC from M13 to M30				
		FAIR Data and Databases	Chemical Exposure & Modelling	2 nd SSbD Bootcamp
Training	Date	22 – 24 May 2024	10-12 June 2024	22-25 October 2024
	Duration (h)	17,5	21	21
	Location	Ljubljana, Slovenia	Brno, Czech Republic	Thessaloniki, Greece
	Scientific Coordination and Local Organisation	Jožef Stefan Institute, SI Janja Snoj Tratnik David Kocman	Masaryk University RECETOX, CZ Petra Růžičková Klára Komprdová	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, EL Denis Sarigiannis Spyros Karakitsios
	Difficulty level	Beginner/ Intermediate	Beginner	Intermediate
Applications	N° applications	32	34	86
	N° selected applications	32	34	80
	N° confirmed applications	26	28	69
Participants	No shows	1	3	2
	Final n° of trainees	25	25	67
	Age (mean ± SD)	36,4 ± 10,4	35,1 ± 7,4	NA
	Gender (women/men/not disclosed)	17/8/0	16/8/1	50/17/0
	N° Countries of work	4 (9 nationalities)	13 (23 nationalities)	21 (NA nationalities)
	Education level	10 PhD 13 MSc 1 BSc 1 undergraduate	13 PhD 12 MSc	48 PhD 19 MSc
	N° PARC researchers (%)	13 (52%)	7 (27%)	3 (4%)
	Affiliation of participants not involved in PARC (N; %)	Academia – 1 (8%) R&D – 2 (17%) Regulatory ^a – 0 Authority/Gov ^b – 7 (58%) Industry ^c – 2 (17%)	Academia – 10 (56%) R&D – 4 (22%) Regulatory ^a – 0 Authority/Gov ^b – 1 (6%) Industry ^c – 1 (6%) NA – 2 (11%)	Academia – 11 (17%) R&D – 17 (27%) Regulatory ^a – 0 Authority/Gov ^b – 15 (23%) Industry ^c – 21 (33%)
Satisfaction	Trainees' satisfaction level^a	4,5 (n=12)	4,6 (n=21)	3,8 (n=35)

a: Regulatory bodies or organisations; b: Authority/ government agencies; c: Business & Industry (including industry associations); NA: not available; SD: standard deviation; ^arange of 0 to 5; assessed by the question *What would be your overall score for the meeting on the scale 0=not satisfied to 5=extremely satisfied?*

2.1.2.1. FAIR Data and Databases

The *FAIR Data and Databases* course was held in Ljubljana, Slovenia from 22nd to 24th May 2024, under the coordination of the Jožef Stefan Institute (Slovenia). The course was disseminated on [PARC website](#), social media and PARCopedia by March 25, 2024, giving potential participants comprehensive details, including content

overview ([Annex 2](#)) and logistical information. Applications were initially accepted until April 12, 2024, with an extended deadline to April 18, 2024. Selected participants (n=32) were notified by April 19, 2024. However, only 26 applicants confirmed attendance, and one did not show on the training, resulting in a final participant count of 25, slightly below the course intended capacity of 30.

Participants ranged in age from 22 to 66 (mean of 36.4), with women making up the majority (17 women and 8 men). Most of the attendees held advanced degrees (PhD or MSc), and about half (52%) were involved in PARC. Those not involved in PARC were mainly affiliated to authority/ government agencies (58%), followed by industry (17%).

This training aimed to enhance participants' understanding of FAIR principles and their practical application in data management, and included theoretical and hands-on sessions, as well as visits to the laboratories of the Department of Environmental Sciences and the experimental nuclear facility, the TRIGA Mark II Reactor, which is part of the Jožef Stefan Institute research infrastructure. The full training agenda is available also in [Annex 2](#). The average satisfaction level of the trainees was measured using the survey previously developed in Task 9.4. Despite a response rate of only about 50%, the feedback indicated a high level of satisfaction, with a mean score of 4.5 (ranging from 0 to 5). A complete overview of the responses obtained in the training satisfaction survey for this course is provided also in [Annex 2](#).

2.1.2.2. Chemical Exposure & Modelling

The *Chemical Exposure & Modelling* course was held in Brno, Czech Republic from 10th to 12th June 2024, under the coordination of Masaryk University/RECETOX (Czech Republic). Details about the course ([Annex 3](#)) and logistical information, were posted on [PARC website](#) and social media platforms by March 26, 2024. Applications were initially open until April 15, with an extended deadline to April 28. Notification of acceptance was sent to 34 selected applicants by April 30. However, only 28 of those selected confirmed their attendance, and three participants were absent on the day, resulting in a final attendance of 25.

Participants were between 27 and 57 years old, with an average age of 35.1. The majority were women (16 women, 8 men). All participants held advanced degrees (PhD or MSc), and only 27% were directly involved in PARC; non-PARC participants worked mainly in academia (56%) and R&D (22%).

This training focused on the identification of input data necessary for exposure assessment, modelling processes and model parameterisation, and the use of physiologically based kinetic models to reconstruct or estimate chemical human exposure levels. It included theoretical sessions, demonstrations and exercises, as well as visits to RECETOX laboratories and biobank. The full training agenda is available also in [Annex 3](#). PARC trainee satisfaction survey was sent to all trainees, and 21 responses were received (response rate of 84%). Results showed a strong level of satisfaction, with an average score of 4.6 (ranging from 0 to 5). A full summary of the survey responses for this course can be found in [Annex 3](#). Support materials have been shared with trainees using the Masaryk University/RECETOX Sharepoint.

2.1.2.3. Second Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) Boot Camp

The *2nd SSbD Bootcamp* was held in Thessaloniki, Greece from 22nd to 25th October 2024, under the coordination of Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece). This training, initially not planned under PARC training plan, was later added given the importance of the topic to the risk assessment community. By July 8, 2024, comprehensive information about the course, including details in [Annex 4](#) and guidance on travel and accommodation, were made available on [PARC website](#) and social media channels. Applications were accepted until July 15, with acceptance

notifications sent to 80 applicants (out of a total of 86) by the end of July. Ultimately, the bootcamp counted with 67 trainees.

The group average age was 37 years old and included 50 women and 17 men. Most participants hold a PhD degree and only 4% were involved in PARC; those not involved in PARC were mainly affiliated to industry (33%), followed by R&D (27%), authority/ government agencies (23%), and academia (17%).

The training focused on the in-depth understanding of the SSbD framework and the stage gate innovation process, demonstrating real-life applications, followed by hands on training for the participants on the PARC SSbD toolbox. [Annex 4](#) contains the full training agenda. Following the course, the PARC trainee satisfaction survey was distributed, and an overall score of 3.8 was obtained (ranging from 0 to 5) in a total of 35 responses received (response rate of 52%). A full summary of the survey responses for this course can be found in [Annex 4](#).

2.1.2.4 Challenges and Lessons Learned

All courses were announced over two months in advance (timeline outlined in **Figure 3**), with a number of applications (for the first two courses) slightly above the available spots. In future trainings, course announcements will be made three to four months in advance (a practice already adopted for courses scheduled later in 2024) to ensure broader dissemination. Additionally, Task 9.4 partners may need to explore further dissemination strategies, such as using institutional mailing lists, professional networks, or targeted outreach through relevant academic and industry channels to maximize visibility and engagement.

Figure 3. Timeline describing Dissemination, Application, Notification, and Training stages of training held under PARC T9.4 in 2024.

Also, there was a notable number of trainees that either withdrew or did not confirm their attendance, likely due to the absence of funding for travel and accommodation. To better understand the reasons for these dropouts, future participants will be asked to confirm their participation through a structured survey upon selection. This survey will gather insights into any barriers they may face, such as financial constraints or logistical challenges that determine their decision to withdraw. Additionally, the 2nd PARC training needs survey will be updated to ask respondents if they participated in any of the previous PARC training courses and to capture their level of interest or any restraints. This information will help tailor future events to address trainee needs and improve attendance rates.

Finally, it is also clear that the response rate to the training satisfaction survey is not always as high as desirable, and therefore efforts will be made to encourage higher response rates in future training (e.g. by filling in the survey by the end of the training).

2.2. Online resources

2.2.1. Overview

In Y2, the PARC Training Plan also focused on creating high-quality e-learning materials for non-formal learning designed to reach a wider audience. This option cuts costs associated with travel and accommodation, and provides flexibility for busy learners, allowing them to engage at their own pace. To address the challenge of limited direct

interaction with instructors, developers were encouraged to include contact information in the materials, ensuring learners still can ask questions and seek guidance.

According to the initial timeline established in AD9.1, up to M30, Task 9.4 partners should have developed the videos on SOPs for occupational biomonitoring studies and a related FAQ sheet, an e-book focusing on *In silico* modelling, and a slide deck on New (non-invasive) matrices. The videos and FAQ sheet are currently nearing completion, while the e-book on *In Silico* modelling is progressing as planned (details on both resources are provided below). However, the slide deck on non-invasive matrices has been rescheduled and is now expected to be ready by January 2025.

It is important to highlight that, since the submission of AD9.1, additional online resources have been incorporated into the training plan. Specifically, a slide deck on non-targeted screening, which will be developed by BPI, EL, and a slide deck on Basic Toxicology, to be contributed by UEF, FI (included above in Figure 2).

2.2.2. Resources developed

2.2.2.1. SOPs for occupational biomonitoring (videos)

Following the development of different standard operating procedures (SOPs) to guide partners involved in the Occupational Studies, namely the Waste Management Survey, currently ongoing under PARC (P4.1.1d), several training videos have been created (listed in **Table 2**) to clarify and reinforce information outlined in the SOPs.

Table 2. Training videos on SOPs for the PARC Waste Management Survey			
Video	Created by	Duration	Visualisations (by October 7, 2024)
Training for PARC Waste Management Survey - Introduction and aims	Susana Viegas (ENSP, PT)	3min45sec	7 (VITO Sharepoint) 14 (YouTube)
SOP1. Selection of participants and recruitment, information to the participants, informed consent	Susana Viegas (ENSP, PT)	9min14sec	11 (VITO Sharepoint) 9 (YouTube)
SOP2. Gathering contextual information	Karen Galea (IOM, UK)	15min21sec	7 (VITO Sharepoint) 4 (YouTube)
SOP3. Blood sampling (Dried blood spots)	Ogier Hanser (INRS, FR)	11min45sec	15 (VITO Sharepoint) 6 (YouTube)
SOP3. Blood sampling	Maria João Silva (INSA, PT)	19min43sec	18 (VITO Sharepoint) 6 (YouTube)
SOP5. Dust sampling (settled dust)	Susana Viegas (ENSP, PT) and Radu Duca (LNS, LU)	11min00sec	9 (VITO Sharepoint) 13 (YouTube)
SOP6. Air sampling	Elke Eriksen (STAMI, NO)	16min15sec	12 (VITO Sharepoint) 7 (YouTube)
SOP7. Hair sampling	Emilie Hardy and Radu Duca (LNS, LU)	11min42sec	12 (VITO Sharepoint) 9 (YouTube)
SOP8. Dermal sampling (wipe samples)	Karen Galea (IOM, UK)	14min24sec	9 (VITO Sharepoint) 12 (YouTube)
SOP8. Dermal sampling (wristbands)	Emilie Hardy (LNS, LU)	9min15sec	13 (VITO Sharepoint) 13 (YouTube)
SOP9. Buccal cell sampling	Henriqueta Louro (INSA, PT)	11min42sec	11 (VITO Sharepoint) 10 (YouTube)
SOP10. Communication plan	Susana Viegas (ENSP, PT)	4min28sec	12 (VITO Sharepoint) 7 (YouTube)

Total 246

The scientific content and preparation of the videos were fully determined and managed by the Waste Management Survey partners (also listed in **Table 2**), under the coordination of the project leaders (Tiina Santonen (TTL, FI) and Susana Viegas (ENSP, PT)). In a subsequent phase, videos were captioned by T9.4 partners and then uploaded to VITO Sharepoint (by July 12, 2024) and the PARCopedia YouTube channel with the collaboration of T2.2 (PARCopedia team; by August 19, 2024) but kept unlisted. This means that videos ([Annex 5](#)) are currently only accessible to Waste Management Survey partners who have received the link via email, while we wait for the video authors to decide whether these materials can be made publicly available. Regardless, videos present a total of 246 visualisations, a good number considering the total of 18 institutions involved in the Waste Management Survey.

The video descriptions on both VITO SharePoint and the PARCopedia YouTube channel included a link to a form where viewers could submit questions, share feedback, and rate their satisfaction with the content. Although the number of responses was relatively low compared to the number of views (8 vs. 246), it's important to note the high overall satisfaction among respondents, with an average rating of 3.875 on a 5-point scale. All questions raised by viewers were addressed during an online Q&A session held on September 13, 2024. These questions are also being used to create a FAQ sheet, which will be available soon.

The delay in releasing the videos and FAQ sheet, initially planned for December 2023 and March 2024, is directly tied to the overall delay in the occupational project, specifically related to the completion of the SOPs. Currently, additional training videos focused on the Healthcare Survey are in preparation and are anticipated to be completed in the coming months.

2.2.2.2. *In silico* modelling (e-book)

This e-book entitled *In silico models: assessment of the results of the VEGA models within an exercise of the PARC project* focuses on the use of specific *in silico* models and read-across tools, applied to three particular substances, namely bisphenol A (BPA), isosorbide, and benzofuranylpropylaminopentane (BPAP). It completes the previously published e-book *In silico models: theory, guidance and applications within VEGAHUB* ([here](#)), by exploring specific cases discussed in WP8, while exploring results obtained, their interpretation, and critical evaluation.

Initially planned for the first trimester of 2024, this material is about to be finished (November/December 2024) and will be listed in the training library (detailed in [section 2.4.2](#)) for broader dissemination.

2.2.3. Challenges and Lessons Learned

When it comes to online resources, some important challenges must be mentioned. One significant issue was the selection of platforms that could host the developed materials. Given the size of the videos and their potential impact on website performance (for both the PARC and PARCopedia sites), it became clear that utilizing a video-sharing platform was essential. Ultimately, the decision was made to use the existing PARCopedia YouTube channel. A similar decision will soon be necessary regarding the platform for hosting additional materials currently in development, such as FAQ sheets and an e-book. The selected platform should not only facilitate easy access and ensure sustainability for the long-term availability of resources, but it should also provide metrics on user engagement and visualizations. These data will be valuable for assessing the effectiveness of the materials and understanding viewer behaviour, enabling us to make informed decisions for future content development and dissemination strategies.

To create a centralized search engine that allows users to easily locate all training materials and avoid the pitfalls of content being scattered across multiple platforms, T9.4 is collaborating closely with T3.2 (*Communication, dissemination, and awareness*) and A8.1.4 (*Knowledge sharing & Education as key factors for efficient SSbD operationalisation*) to develop a comprehensive training library. This library will serve as a centralized repository for these and other training resources, streamlining access for users and enhancing their learning experience. Further details on this initiative can be found in [section 2.4.2](#). By consolidating materials in this way, we aim to improve resource discoverability, foster user engagement, and ensure that valuable information is readily available to all interested parties.

Another challenge involves the dissemination of materials, particularly webinar recordings; considering the interest they raise in the entire risk assessment community, T9.4 would like to make some of them publicly available beyond the PARC partners. However, the decision to do so ultimately rests with the organizer or presenter. In this context, T9.4 will focus on cultivating a collaborative mindset among all partners over the next year. We will encourage them to recognize the broader benefits of openly sharing resources while also clarifying the option to license materials under Creative Commons, which offers clear guidelines for use and reusability. By emphasizing the potential for increased reach, engagement, and impact, we aim to foster a culture of knowledge sharing that extends beyond the PARC network, ultimately benefiting a wider community of researchers and risk assessors. Additionally, T9.4 leadership team will offer guidance to partners on best practices for preparing these materials, with a focus on avoiding potential copyright issues should the resources be made publicly accessible (meeting scheduled for December 2024). This guidance will include recommended steps for sourcing content, citing references, and ensuring compliance with copyright regulations, helping to safeguard the integrity and accessibility of the materials for a wider audience.

2.3. Staff exchange

According to the initially planned, the mechanism for staff exchange, previously detailed in AD9.1, was disseminated on PARC website (July 18, 2024) and PARC sampler (Spring/Summer 2024; August 2, 2024). In short, the staff exchange mechanism was disseminated as planned, inviting laboratories interested in hosting trainees to complete a survey detailing their skills, resources, working languages, and specific requirements. Although a few labs have requested additional information, no formal applications have been submitted yet. Nevertheless, some informal exchange has been carried out between PARC partners, as it is the case of Nicola Montemurro from IDAEA-CSIC, that received training on the analysis of unknown compounds using ion-mobility LC-MS methods, in the Laboratory of Analytical Chemistry of the Department of Chemistry from the University of Athens, under the supervision of Nikiforos Alygizakis, for three months (from April 1, 2024 to June 30, 2024)

In the coming months, Task 9.4 co-leaders, along with partners, will explore new strategies to enhance dissemination and encourage greater interest in this training option. One major challenge remains the need for clearly identifying funding opportunities for trainees, which is limiting engagement. To address this, partners will continue efforts to identify funding resources to support participants in the exchange program.

2.4. Existing Training

2.4.1. Mapping existing events

By leveraging the combined knowledge of both T9.4 partners on current events and incorporating valuable input from the community, including details submitted via a [form](#) available on the PARC website, information about upcoming training events has been posted on the PARC website under the "News & Events" section, specifically under "Events" and "Trainings." This platform ensures that all relevant training opportunities are easily accessible to the public.

T9.4 acknowledges that the activity of sharing information on external events has not been as robust as planned. Moving forward, T9.4 is committed to improving this by implementing new strategies to gather and share more information on relevant external events. These strategies will include actively seeking input from partners, community members, and external sources to ensure that the PARC website is consistently updated with valuable opportunities.

2.4.2. Mapping existing resources

Given the extensive array of existing training resources on risk assessment topics and the new materials planned for development under PARC, T9.4 indicated in AD9.1 the development and launch of a training library on the PARC website, accessible to all website users, that for each resource would feature a brief contextualisation, along with information about the target audience and difficulty level.

Over the past year, T9.4 and Activity 8.1.4 (*SSbD knowledge sharing platform*), which also seeks to establish a knowledge platform on Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) that includes training materials, have collaborated to discuss and refine the structure and layout of the training library. Concurrently, they have been identifying the materials that will be featured in this library. It is important to note that this library will not function as a traditional repository; instead, it will serve as a centralised hub for training materials. Users will have the ability to locate specific resources using various filters, such as domains, topics, groups of substances, target audience, type of material, level of expertise, accessibility, and estimated reading time. These filtering options will facilitate easy navigation through the library, ensuring users can efficiently find materials that align with their learning needs and professional development goals.

Currently, T9.4 and A8.1.4 are discussing with T3.2 regarding the feasibility and requirements for implementing the training library. These discussions focus on the library's structure and layout, long-term sustainability, the possibility of collecting relevant metrics to assess the effectiveness of the library in supporting learning and professional development and establishing a clear timeline for its development and launch. Additional key considerations include strategies for maintaining up-to-date content and fostering ongoing user engagement over time to ensure the library remains a valuable and dynamic resource.

2.5. Other training initiatives in PARC

Since the start of the partnership, several PARC members have independently organised webinars and short online courses without the involvement or collaboration of Task 9.4. While these efforts do contribute to the overarching goal of building capacity in risk assessment - particularly by expanding participants' knowledge on specific topics - they pose challenges in two key areas: i) the collection of essential indicators for tracking project progress and ii) the harmonisation of training activities conducted under the PARC initiative.

To enhance the collection of indicators and streamline communication with partners organising various training events not included in the PARC Training Plan, Task 9.4 has developed a file to capture information on past events and a form for submitting details of upcoming events. These tools have been approved by the co-leaders of Task 1.3 (*Impact Evaluation and Monitoring of the performance Indicators of the Partnership*) and Task 3.2 (*Communication, dissemination, and awareness*) and sent to all partners on October 9, 2024 by the PARC Coordination Team. For this purpose, various event formats were considered: courses (a series of lessons aimed at enhancing skills and knowledge in a specific area), webinars (live online presentations that enable real-time interaction with participants), and workshops (which emphasize not only topic presentation but also active discussion). Respondents were advised to differentiate between webinars and courses based on key criteria, such as the depth of information provided (comprehensive in courses, concise in webinars), the level of interaction between presenters and participants (typically high in courses and lower in webinars), and the number of attendees (generally smaller for courses).

For past events, partners were requested to submit detailed information, including the event type, title, a brief description, the level of expertise required, date, duration, target audience, format, and the name and contact details of the scientific coordinators. Additionally, they should provide data on attendance, including the number of participants and any other relevant details, if available. Partners were also asked to share information on any training materials produced, specifying the type of materials, if they were made available, and, if yes, where and to

whom. These comprehensive data will support better monitoring and evaluation of training activities, offering insights into the range and reach of materials produced. Additionally, it will support further planning on how these resources might be made more broadly accessible, extending the impact of the training initiatives.

Table 3 outlines all additional training activities identified by partners as of November 8, 2024, totalling around 30 initiatives. These activities were primarily aimed at either PARC partners or specific Task or project groups, with the exception of the PARCopedia webinar that was open to the risk assessment community. While this table provides a thorough summary of the training reported so far, it is possible that other training events have taken place but have not been documented here yet. Efforts will continue to update this list to capture a complete record of training initiatives across the consortium.

Table 3. Additional Training activities in PARC (from M13^a; June 2023 to M30; October 2024)

Type	Title	Format	Date	Duration	Scientific Coordination	Audience	N° attendees
Webinar	Validation for in vitro test methods (NAMs): Awareness Training 1	R	19/06/2023	1 h	Miriam Jacobs, UKHSA (UK)	PARC partners	125-150
Webinar	Communicate to gain impact	R	26/09/2023	1,5 h	Tamás Szigeti, NPHC (HU)	WP3 contact points WP co-leaders Task co-leaders Project leaders National Hub Coordinators	50
Webinar	Systematic searching literature	R	13/10/2023	1 h	Tessa Pronk, KWR (NL)	PARC T6.1 subgroup genotox qAOP	23
Webinar	Validation for in vitro test methods (NAMs): Awareness Training 2	R	25/01/2024	1 h	Miriam Jacobs, UKHSA (UK)	PARC partners	75-80
Webinar	Validation for in vitro test methods (NAMs): Awareness Training 3	R	22/02/2024	1h	Miriam Jacobs, UKHSA (UK)	PARC partners	90-100
Webinar	Validation for in vitro test methods (NAMs): Awareness Training 4	R	05/03/2024	1 h	Miriam Jacobs, UKHSA (UK)	PARC partners	50-60
Webinar	OPEX Calculator	R	22/03/2024	1,5 h	Agathi Charistou, BPI (EL)	PARC P6.2.1.b partners	15
Webinar	FAIR Data & Tools Webinar Series V. Making (nano)toxicity data FAIR – experiences from Gov4Nano & Data Re-use examples	R	23/03/2024	1 h	Iseult Lynch, UoB (UK)	NA	NA
Webinar	PACEM Tool	R	26/03/2024	1,5 h	Bas Zoutendijk, RIVM (NL)	PARC P6.2.1.b partners	20
Webinar	TREXMO (TRanslation of EXposure MOdels) Tool	R	27/03/2024	1,5 h	David Vernez, Unisanté (CH)	PARC P6.2.1.b partners	15
Webinar	Validation for in vitro test methods (NAMs): Awareness Training 5	R	10/04/2024	1 h	Miriam Jacobs, UKHSA (UK)	PARC partners	50-60
Webinar	ART Tool	R	10/04/2024	1,5 h	Ruby Vermoolen, TNO (NL)	PARC P6.2.1.b partners	15
Webinar	Focus Groups as a qualitative data collection method: conduction and transcription ^b	R	16/04/2024	2 h	FMUL and ENSP (PT)	Countries hosting the focus groups (1st round)	14
Webinar	MCRA (Monte Carlo Risk Assessment)	R	22/04/2024	1,5 h	Johannes Kruijselbrink, WR-BIOM (NL)	PARC P6.2.1.b partners	20
Webinar	RiskofDerm (Risk Assessment of Occupational Dermal Exposure to Chemicals) Tool	R	06/06/2024	1,5 h	Hasnaa Chettou, Unisanté (CH)	PARC P6.2.1.b partners	10
Webinar	RSExpo	R	13/06/2024	1,5 h	Clément Blassiau, Anses (FR)	PARC P6.2.1.b partners	20
Webinar	Lunch lecture series on Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) Lecture 1 of 5: Introduction into NGRA	R	25/06/2024	0,75 h	Ellen Fritsche, UNIBAS (CH)	PARC P6.4.2.a	93
Webinar	PARCopedia webinar	R	28/06/2024	1,5 h	Isabella Apruzzese, BfR (DE)	PARC and beyond	> 200
Webinar	Lunch lecture series on Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) Lecture 2 of 5: Kinetic Modelling	R	03/07/2024	0,75 h	Ellen Fritsche, UNIBAS (CH)	PARC P6.4.2.a	82
Webinar	Lunch lecture series on Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA)	R	20/08/2024	0,75 h	Ellen Fritsche, UNIBAS (CH)	PARC P6.4.2.a	74

	Lecture 3 of 5: AOP (Adverse Outcome Pathways) generation: Bottom-up approach, Case study: Deltametrin and DNT							
Other	Kick-Off AOP_HUB	R	22/08/2024	1 h	Ellen Fritsche, UNIBAS (CH)	PARC P6.4.2.a	120	
Other (Workshop)	International Stakeholder Network - Developmental and Reproductive Toxicity Workshop (ISTNET-DART)		12-13/09/2024	15.5 h	Ellen Fritsche, UNIBAS (CH)	PARC P6.4.2.a	55	
Webinar	SOPs (standard operating procedure) Training and Q&A session	R	13/09/2024	1,75 h	Kukka Aimonen, TTL (FI)	PARC T4.1.1.4 Waste management survey	46	
Webinar	Lunch lecture series on Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) Lecture 4 of 5: AOP (Adverse Outcome Pathways) generation: Top-down approach, Case study: Parkinson AOP	R	23/09/2024	0,75 h	Ellen Fritsche, UNIBAS (CH)	PARC P6.4.2.a	59	
Webinar	Lunch lecture series on Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) Lecture 5 of 5: AOP (Adverse Outcome Pathways) generation: Inside-out approach, Case study: AOPs starting from DNT IVB endpoints	R	02/10/2024	0,75 h	Ellen Fritsche, UNIBAS (CH)	PARC P6.4.2.a	40	
Course	Workshop implementation of FAIR PBK models in SBML using Antimony	P	07-08/10/2024	2 days	Anne Zwartsen, RIVM (NL)	PARC P6.2.2 and P6.2.3	11	
Webinar	Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design, from Theory to Practice: Case Studies and Added-Value in European R&D&I Projects	R	07/10/2024	1 h	Susanne Resch, BNN (AT)	PARC and beyond	42	
Other (Workshop)	Governing Board Workshop on Nanomaterials	R	29/10/2024	2 h	Iseult Lynch, BHAM (UK) & Susana Loureiro, UAVR (PT)	PARC Governing Board members and PARC partners	65	
Other (Workshop)	Governing Board Workshop on PFAS	R	31/10/2024	2 h	Lutz Ahrens, SLU (SE) & Thorhallur Ingi Halldórsson, HI (IS)	PARC Governing Board members and PARC partners	NA	
Other (Workshop)	Governing Board Workshop on Microplastics	R	06/11/2024	2 h	Dorte Herzke, FHI (NO)	PARC Governing Board members and PARC partners	NA	
Other (Webinar series)	Weekly APO_HUB meeting	R	29/08/2024 05/09/2024 19/09/2024 26/09/2024 03/10/2024 10/10/2024 07/11/2024	1 h	Ellen Fritsche, UNIBAS (CH)	PARC P6.4.2.a	Between 10 and 120	

^aup to M12, no additional activities were identified, other than the previously listed in D9.3; ^bsatisfaction was assessed using the PARC satisfaction survey model with a satisfaction of 4,2 (ranging from 0 to 5; response rate of 36%); P: in-person; R: remote; NA – not available.

To effectively coordinate and harmonize all training events held under PARC, Task 9.4 has also created a form for collecting information on upcoming training initiatives. This form will help track partners' plans to organize future training sessions, ensuring timely alignment of content and dissemination strategies across all partners, and ensure consistency in the application process, satisfaction assessment, and the issuance of training certificates. By gathering these details in advance, the initiative will be better positioned to streamline efforts and maximize the impact of upcoming training activities.

In addition to the initiatives outlined in **Table 3**, 11 PARC researchers have successfully earned their qualifications as 3-PFF Facilitators through the 3-Point FAIRification Framework, an initiative led by WP7 in collaboration with the GO FAIR Foundation. This framework has been specifically tailored to address the needs and research areas relevant to PARC, equipping the researchers with the expertise to promote and support the implementation of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data practices in their work in PARC projects or work packages.

3. Future Activities

In the coming year, partners will maintain their focus on advancing all the initiatives outlined to date. This includes mapping existing external training opportunities, actively promoting and disseminating the staff exchange program

within the consortium, and executing the training plan, which encompasses the delivery of identified courses and the development of new educational resources. These efforts will continue to build on the progress made so far, ensuring that the training objectives are met, and the resources remain aligned with the evolving needs of the project.

Regarding the training plan, Task 9.4 co-leaders will actively encourage their partners to contribute additional training topics based on their expertise and availability. They will also work to identify additional synergies to enhance capacity building and promote skill development.

In parallel, PARC training needs survey will be redistributed and shared again (early 2025) with partners and stakeholders to gather updated information. This data will form the foundation for the second training plan, which will guide the implementation of training activities from October 2025 to October 2027. By collecting insights on evolving needs and priorities, the survey will ensure that the upcoming training plan is aligned with the latest developments and demands within the consortium and broader stakeholder community.

4. Final Remarks

In conclusion, significant progress has been made towards achieving the goals outlined for this task. In this period, some important achievements were made, including the organisation of the first in-person training courses, the development of the first educational resources, and the promotion of a staff exchange process for PARC partners. However, some challenges remain, particularly in harmonizing communication and ensuring the long-term accessibility of materials. These issues will be addressed in the coming months through increased collaboration and strategic planning.

Looking ahead, Task 9.4 co-leaders and partners will continue working on expanding PARC 1st training plan, mapping existing training, and also on preparing PARC 2nd training plan with the distribution of a new training needs survey to partners and stakeholders, always focusing on the overarching goal of Task 9.4 of enhancing and strengthening the competencies, skills, and knowledge of both partners and stakeholders to ensure a capable and informed risk assessment community.

Annex 1.

Roadmap for course organisation

Figure A1.1 presents a detailed description of a step-by-step process of setting up and carrying out a training course in PARC. The procedure includes five main stages: Dissemination; Application; Selection and Notification; Training; Post Training, and involves T9.4, T3.2 and the course Scientific/Local Coordinators.

Figure A1.1. Roadmap for course organisation in PARC.

In short, the process begins with Task 9.4 sending essential materials to Training Scientific Coordinators (TSC), including templates for the application form, practical information, and agenda for completion; at the same time, TSC are also asked to review the course details previously discussed with T9.4. With this information, Task 9.4 prepares an application form in RedCap and drafts a news item for dissemination, and with the agreement of the TSC sends all the materials to Task 3.2 that finalises the training communication leaflet and news item and ensures their timely publication on PARC website.

After the application period, Task 9.4 compiles applications and sends them to TSC that selects applicants based on their background and motivation. Selected trainees are notified by Task 9.4 that also manages confirmations. At this point, TSC are asked to confirm fields to include in the training evaluation form, later on prepared by Task 9.4 partner NIJZ, SI, and to prepare training certificates based on the existing template.

Throughout the course, sessions may be recorded, slides and supporting materials are shared, and documentation (photos, videos, attendance, and satisfaction) is gathered. After the course, feedback from the satisfaction survey is analysed to evaluate success and identify possible improvements for the future. Finally, communication materials summarizing outcomes are prepared for public dissemination by Task 9.4 and TSC. This structured approach ensures coordinated planning, execution, and follow-up with clear roles across all stages; in any case, some of the roles may be slightly changed to accommodate the preferences of the TSC. Please note that, in all PARC training courses held so far, the TSC also served as the local organizer. This setup will adjust slightly if the TSC is not the local organizer in future cases.

Annex 2.

Additional Information on the *FAIR Data and Databases* course

FAIR DATA AND DATABASES TRAINING COURSE

DOC. VERSION 01

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Training Course

FAIR Data and Databases

Course Details

This partnership has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101057014.

FAIR Data and Databases	
Summary	<p>The training program addresses the critical need for FAIRification of data to enhance the exchange and re-use of information across diverse scientific disciplines. Acknowledging the significance of integrating heterogeneous data for improved accessibility and reusability, the curriculum focuses on FAIR data principles, terminology, and tools.</p> <p>Aligned with the objectives of PARC, the training aims to strengthen capacities for chemical risk assessment and contribute to EU-wide transdisciplinary knowledge-management platforms. The program will improve understanding of the FAIR principles among PARC (and other) partners, facilitate better use of existing data, improve data harmonization, and train researchers in effective and reliable data management approaches.</p>
Tentative Contents	<p>This training program is designed to provide participants with a thorough understanding of the FAIR data principles, practices and terminology, with a focus on the approaches adopted by / developed within PARC to support Chemical Risk Assessment. In relation to efficient data management, the training will provide insight into use of Python and SQL (Structured Query Language) in the context of relational databases.</p> <p>In addition to the core content, this training program will feature 1) Training on the use of 'FAIR Implementation Profiles' (FIPs) to evaluate the FAIRness of existing databases executed by PARC 3PFF Trainers / Facilitators who have been certified by the Go Fair Foundation (GFF), and 2) hands-on training on solutions for extraction of geospatial data from existing European databases for the specific needs of PARC activities.</p>
Learning outcomes	<p>Participants can expect to gain a comprehensive understanding of FAIR data concepts and principles, and practical skills in implementing FAIR data practice, including assessment of the FAIRness of existing databases using the FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) tool.</p> <p>Basic knowledge on GIS based data exploitation in general and for specific needs of PARC project activities.</p>
Target audience	<p>Researchers and students producing experimental data relating to chemicals exposure, hazard and risk assessment, or extracting and utilising data stored in existing databases for chemicals risk assessment. Expertise in computer and data sciences is an asset.</p>
Duration	3 days
Difficulty level	Beginner to Intermediate
Pre-requisites	Basic knowledge on data use and extraction from database(s) and/or awareness of the need for data management.
Selection process	<p>Selection through application based on the main interest and field of expertise, existing skills (lab-based data generation, statistics and data handling or processing, data visualisation, data curation), work experience (students vs. more experienced) and motivation. PARC partners (non WP7) will be prioritized, geographical representation across the European regions will also be considered.</p>
Maximum number of participants	30
Scientific coordinator and local organizer	<p>Jožef Stefan Institute, SI Janja Snoj Tratnik (janja.tratnik@ijs.si) David Kocman (david.kocman@ijs.si)</p>
Dates and location	<p>22th – 24th May 2024 Ljubljana, Slovenia</p>

This meeting is part of the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals. This partnership has received funding from the European Union.

FAIR DATA AND DATABASES

2024-04-19
DOC. VERSION 01

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

FAIR data and Databases

Course Programme

P-A-R-C
Partnership
for the
Assessment
of
Risks
from
Chemicals

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

This partnership has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101057014.

Course Details

Title	FAIR data and Databases
Date	22-24 May 2024
Time	Details below
Venue	Jožef Stefan Institute, Reactor Center, Brinje 40, 1262 Dol pri Ljubljani, Slovenia
Scientific Coordinators	Janja Snoj Tratnik (janja.tratnik@ijs.si) David Kocman (david.kocman@ijs.si)

Programme

Day 1: 22.05.2024

Time	Topic	Speakers	Activity type
09:00 – 09:15	Welcome from the Head of Department	Milena Horvat (JSI)	Welcome
09:15 – 10:30	Introduction to the training course, FAIR awareness	Iseult Lynch (UoB) Panče Panev (JSI)	Introduction
10:30 – 11:00	Coffee-Break		
11:00 – 12:30	FAIR awareness	Iseult Lynch, Tassos Papadiamantis (UoB) Panče Panev (JSI)	FAIR principles
12:30 – 13:30	Lunch		
13:30 – 15:00	Data management- HBM data	<i>To be determined</i> (VITO)	Theory, principles and practical examples
15:00 – 15:30	Coffee-Break		
15:30 – 17:00	Data management – environmental data	<i>To be determined</i> (MU)	Theory, principles and practical examples

Day 2: 23.05.2024

Time	Topic	Speakers	Activity type
09:00 – 10:30	Fair implementation profiles (FIPs) with practical part	Panče Panov (JSI) Tassos Papadiamantis, Iseult Lynch (UoB)	Practical examples
10:30 – 11:00	Coffee-Break		
11:00 – 12:30	Introduction to extraction of geospatial data	David Kocman, Janja Snoj Tratnik (JSI)	Theory
12:30 – 13:30	Lunch		
13:30 – 15:00	Demonstration on extraction of geospatial data: Address-based data extraction by data owners	David Kocman, Jure Ftičar (JSI)	Hands-on training
15:00 – 15:30	Coffee-Break		
15:30 – 17:00	Interaction with participants	All	Discussion panel

Day 3: 24.05.2024

Time	Topic	Speakers	Activity type
09:00 – 10:30	FAIR Metadata – PARC example	<i>To be determined</i> (VITO)	Practical example
10:30 – 11:00	Coffee-Break		
11:00 – 12:30	Practical example (<i>awaiting confirmation</i>)	<i>To be determined</i>	Practical example
12:30 – 13:30	Lunch		

This course is part of the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals. This partnership has received funding from the European Union.

Training Evaluation Survey Results

FAIR Data and Databases

22-24.04.2024

METHODOLOGY

For the reporting on trainees' satisfaction, we gathered feedback on five primary categories: satisfaction with course organisation, course content/structure, delivery methods and trainers, satisfaction with exercises, tools, and overall satisfaction. These categories were assessed through a survey, where respondents rated their level of agreement on a Likert scale, ranging from "1. Strongly disagree" to "5. Strongly agree" in the first four sections. In the assessment of the overall satisfaction, the Likert scale varied from "1. Very dissatisfied" to "5. Very satisfied."

Below, an overview of the aggregated data collected from the satisfaction survey is presented for each of the five categories. Strengths of the training and also areas for improvement are also highlighted to further optimise future sessions. Where applicable, qualitative feedback from participants has been included to provide context and enhance understanding of the numerical data.

RESULTS

I. Overall Satisfaction

Key Additional Comments: Do you have any suggestions on how to improve this course?

- Thank you!
- Increase level of difficulty.

Legend: 1- Very dissatisfied, 2- Dissatisfied, 3- Neutral, 4- Satisfied, 5- Very satisfied

II. Detailed Satisfaction

Strong Points:

Venue and Logistics: High satisfaction with the venue conditions (92% approval), showing effective logistical planning.

Course Content: The course content was well-received, with 83% finding it interesting and useful.

Trainer Interaction: Strong satisfaction with trainer engagement; 83% appreciated discussion opportunities, and 75% found explanations clear.

Timely Information Delivery: Most participants (83%) were pleased with the timing of information and materials.

Points for Improvement:

Balance of Activities: 42% of respondents were neutral on the balance between presentations and activities, indicating a need to re-evaluate course structure.

Exercises: Opinions on exercises were varied; while 50% were satisfied, 42% were neutral, and 1 participant was dissatisfied, indicating the exercises could be refined or better aligned with participant needs.

Tool Usability: Mixed feedback on the tool's effectiveness, user-friendliness, and applicability to work, with 33-50% neutrality, highlighting an opportunity for clearer guidance or more user-friendly adaptation

A. Satisfaction with course organisation

Key Additional Comments:

- Transport arranged from the city to the venue very useful.

B. Satisfaction with course content/structure, delivery methods and trainers

Key Additional Comments:

- More time dedicated to exploration of tools.

C. Satisfaction with exercises

D. Satisfaction with tools

Key Additional Comments:

- Increase guidance on the tool use.

III. Input on Additional Training Needs

1. Spatial data.
2. Connection between data sharing and GDPR related issues.

Annex 3.

Additional Information on the *Chemical Exposure & Modelling* course

CHEMICAL EXPOSURE & MODELING TRAINING COURSE

DOC. VERSION 01

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Training Course

Chemical Exposure & Modeling

Course Details

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

This partnership has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101057014.

Chemical Exposure & Modeling	
Summary	Exposure assessment is a key component of the risk assessment process, and integrated exposure models rely on environmental data and exposure factors to produce relevant exposure assessments. Understanding the availability and uncertainties in these data is crucial to allow correct selection of inputs and prioritization of exposure pathways within an exposure modeling framework. Implementation of current exposure models requires a breadth of knowledge across diverse pathways, chemicals, and matrices, covering dietary exposure, exposures from consumer products, and environmental levels in indoor and outdoor environments. In recent years, Physiologically Based Kinetic (PBK, also pharmacokinetic PBPK or toxicokinetic PBTK) models have been used in the context of risk assessment to determine biomonitoring equivalents (BE) relevant as regulatory threshold values linked with HBM data. Modelling results can be used to refine the safety levels, either as exposure concentration or tissue concentration under which no adverse effect is expected according to state-of-the art knowledge. PBK models can also compare population subgroups, characterize inter-individual variability, perform extrapolations, and support read-across between similar substances by comparing their concentration kinetic profiles. An integral part of PBK models is their validation and evaluation of uncertainty propagation throughout the modelling process, considering the inaccuracy of input data, model parameters and model structure, necessary for achieving relevant results with a known degree of certainty.
Tentative Contents	The first part of the training will focus on identifying input data necessary for exposure assessments, including food, indoor and outdoor environments and consumer products. A critical overview will be given to exposure factors and how environmental data can be interpreted and spatially evaluated in the context of exposure assessment. The second part of the training program focuses on learning about the modelling processes, identifying the input data required for model parameterisation and using PBPK models for selected substances to reconstruct or estimate the amount of a chemical to which a person has been exposed (i.e. the exposure dose).
Learning outcomes	Upon completion of the course, the participant should be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - identify sources of exposure data relevant for exposure modelling - understand spatial data and be able to process and display such data - critically assess exposure factors and model input data - perform basic exposure assessment for example compounds - describe the basic concepts and principles of PBPK models - use models for estimation of internal levels of chemicals - critically assess model uncertainties
Target audience	Researchers and students
Duration	3 days
Difficulty level	Beginner
Pre-requisites /Requirements	Basic knowledge on data use Have a personal computer
Selection process	Selection based on written request which will include participant's background, working experience and motivation. Priority will be on PARC partners.
Maximum number of participants	20
Scientific coordinator & contacts	Masaryk University RECETOX, CZ Petra Růžičková (petra.ruzickova@recetox.muni.cz) Klára Komprdová (klara.komprdova@recetox.muni.cz)
Dates and location	10-12 June 2024 Brno, Czech Republic, Masaryk University, RECETOX

This meeting is part of the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals. This partnership has received funding from the European Union.

CHEMICAL EXPOSURE AND MODELLING
PARC TRAINING AND 20TH RECETOX SUMMER SCHOOL

2024-05-27
DOC. VERSION 02

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Chemical Exposure and Modelling

Course Programme

This partnership has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101057014.

Course Details

Title	20 th RECETOX Summer School and PARC Training Chemical Exposure and Modelling		
Date	Monday, 10 June, 2024 — Wednesday, 12 June, 2024		
Time	Details below		
Venue	RECETOX, Masaryk University Brno, Czech Republic Kamenice 753/5, pavilion D29	MUNI RECETOX	Research infrastructure
Scientific Coordinators	Masaryk University RECETOX, CZ Petra Růžicková (petra.ruzickova@recetox.muni.cz) Klára Komprdová (klara.komprdova@recetox.muni.cz)		

Lecturers

Prof Martin Scheringer, Swiss Federal Institute of Technology/RECETOX, Masaryk University, Switzerland/Czech Republic

Prof. Dr. Beate Escher, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research, Germany

Dr. Rok Novak - Jožef Stefan Institute, Slovenia

Dr. Joost Westerhout, National Institute for Public Health and the Environment, Netherlands

Dr. Aude Ratier, National Institute for Industrial Environment and Risks, France

Dr. Jasper Engel, Wageningen University & Research, Netherlands

Dr. Johannes Kruisselbrink, Wageningen University & Research, Netherlands

Dr. Lisa Melymuk, RECETOX, MU, CZ

Dr. Ondřej Mikeš, RECETOX, MU, CZ

Dr. Daniel Szabó, RECETOX, MU, CZ

Programme

Day 1: 10.06.2024 (Monday), RECETOX, lecture room RCX 1, 2nd floor

Topic of the day: **Sources and drivers of human exposure to chemicals**

Time	Topic	Speakers	Activity type
9:00 — 9:30 (30')	Registration		
9:30 — 11:00 (90')	Introduction to Chemical exposure and modelling	Martin Scheringer , ICB ETH (CH) RECETOX (CZ)	Lecture
11:00 — 11:30 (30')	Break		
11:30 — 13:00 (90')	Complex mixtures in human biomonitoring	Beate Escher , Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research — UFZ (DE)	Lecture
13:00 — 14:30 (90')	Lunch		

Time	Topic	Speakers	Activity type
14:00 – 14:30 (30')	<i>(optional) Guided biobank tour (RECETOX RI, Population Studies)</i>		Biobank Tour
14:30 – 16:00 (90')	Sources of chemical exposure to humans	Lisa Melymuk, RECETOX (CZ)	Lecture
16:00 – 16:30 (30')	Break		
16:30 – 17:30 (60')	Introduction to toxicokinetics and modelling	Joost Westerhout, RIVM (NL)	Lecture

Day 2: 11.06.2024 (Tuesday), RECETOX, lecture room RCX 1, 2nd floor

Topic of the day: **Assessing (internal) exposure to chemicals, hands-on training**

Time	Topic	Speakers	Activity type
9:00 – 10:30 (90')	How to build and use a Physiologically Based Toxicokinetic (PBTK) model?	Joost Westerhout, RIVM (NL)	Lecture
10:30 – 11:00 (30')	Break		
10:50 – 11:00 (10')	Group photo		
11:00 – 12:30 (90')	Considering variability and uncertainty in PBTK model	Aude Ratier, INERIS (FR)	Lecture
12:30 – 14:00 (90')	Lunch		
13:30 – 14:00 (30')	<i>(optional) Guided lab tour (RECETOX RI, Trace Analytical Labs)</i>		Lab Tour
14:00 – 15:30 (90')	Basic dietary exposure assessment for single chemicals and mixtures (hands-on exercise using MCRA)	Jasper Engel, WUR (NL) Johannes Kruisselbrink, WUR (NL)	Exercise
15:30 – 16:00 (30')	Break		
16:00 – 17:30 (90')	Example of PBTK modelling in exposure assessment (hand-on exercise using MCRA)	Jasper Engel, WUR (NL) Johannes Kruisselbrink, WUR (NL)	Exercise
17:30 – 18:00 (30')	<i>(optional) Discussion</i>	Klára Komprdová, RECETOX (CZ) + all lecturers from the second day	Discussion

Day 3: 12.06.2024 (Wednesday), RECETOX, lecture room RCX 1, 2nd floor

Topic of the day: **Spatial information in human health risk assessment**

Time	Topic	Speakers	Activity type
9:00 – 10:30 (90')	Introduction to GIS and Geospatial analysis	Ondřej Mikeš, RECETOX (CZ) Daniel Szabó, RECETOX (CZ)	Lecture
10:30 – 11:00 (30')	Break		
11:00 – 12:30 (90')	Practical examples and use cases of GIS in research	Rok Novak, JSI (SI) Ondřej Mikeš, RECETOX (CZ) Daniel Szabó, RECETOX (CZ)	Demonstration
12:30 – 14:00 (90')	Lunch		
14:00 – 15:30 (30')	PC Exercises	Rok Novak, JSI (SI) Ondřej Mikeš, RECETOX (CZ) Daniel Szabó, RECETOX (CZ)	Exercise
15:30 – 16:00 (30')	Break		
	End of Training		

MUNI | RECETOX

Research
infrastructure

This course is the 20th RECETOX Summer School

This partnership has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101057014.

This course is part of the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals. This partnership has received funding from the European Union.

Training Evaluation Survey Results Chemical Exposure & Modelling

10-12.06.2024

METHODOLOGY

For the reporting on trainees' satisfaction, we gathered feedback on five primary categories: satisfaction with course organisation, course content/structure, delivery methods and trainers, satisfaction with exercises, tools, and overall satisfaction. These categories were assessed through a survey, where respondents rated their level of agreement on a Likert scale, ranging from "1. Strongly disagree" to "5. Strongly agree" in the first four sections. In the assessment of the overall satisfaction, the Likert scale varied from "1. Very dissatisfied" to "5. Very satisfied."

Below, an overview of the aggregated data collected from the satisfaction survey is presented for each of the five categories. Strengths of the training and also areas for improvement are also highlighted to further optimise future sessions. Where applicable, qualitative feedback from participants has been included to provide context and enhance understanding of the numerical data.

RESULTS

I. Overall Satisfaction

Key Additional Comments: Do you have any suggestions on how to improve this course?

- Thank you!
- Short self-presentation of the participants.

II. Detailed Satisfaction

Strong Points:

- **Venue and Logistics:** Positive feedback, with 95% of participants agreeing it provided all necessary conditions. This highlights strong logistical planning and effective event coordination.
- **Timely Information Delivery:** 91% of respondents were satisfied with it, indicating efficient communication and preparation.
- **Interest in Future Courses:** A strong majority (81%) expressed interest in attending a more advanced version of the course, reflecting high engagement and perceived value.
- **Trainer Interaction and Support:** Highly rated, with 98% of participants agreeing that trainers provided ample opportunities for questions and discussions.
- **Tool Usability:** The tools used during the course were generally well-received. For example, 86% agreed that processing time was reasonable, and 81% felt they could easily find the requested information.

Points for Improvement

- **Course Content and New Information:** While 67% strongly agreed that the course content included new information, a notable 24% were neutral or less satisfied, suggesting room for more innovative material.
- **Balance of Activities:** The balance between presentations and hands-on activities could be improved, as 29% of respondents gave neutral or negative feedback in this area.
- **Time Allocation for Exercises:** While 72% felt that the time allocated for exercises was sufficient, 29% were neutral or dissatisfied, indicating that some participants felt rushed or would have preferred more time.
- **Satisfaction with Exercises:** Exercise satisfaction was generally high, but 34% of participants provided neutral or negative feedback, suggesting a need for more tailored or engaging activities.
- **Tool Usability Challenges:** Some participants found the tools less user-friendly or difficult to apply in their work, with 29% providing neutral or negative responses.

A. Satisfaction with course organisation

Key Additional Comments:

- Support materials sent prior to the training.

B. Satisfaction with course content/structure, delivery methods and trainers

Key Additional Comments:

- Introductory overview of PARC.
- Larger time allocation.

C. Satisfaction with exercises

Key Additional Comments:

- Larger time allocation.
- Follow-up at home exercises to advance and reinforce skills.

D. Satisfaction with tools

Key Additional Comments:

- Summary of the input file format and the fields (one or multiple) where this input file can be imported.

III. Input on Additional Training Needs

1. Data, risk assessment (hbgv, hbmvg, the latest regulation on the 1st set of chemicals priority in parc).

Annex 4.

Additional Information on the 2nd SSbD Bootcamp

SSBD BOOT CAMP

2024-07-08

DOC. VERSION 01

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

PARC SSbD boot camp

Course Details

Co-funded by
the European Union

This partnership has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101057014.

PARC SSbD bootcamp	
Summary	This Boot Camp will provide you with a unique opportunity to get fundamental insights in SSbD thinking, learn how to apply the EU SSbD framework from experts in the field, share knowledge and experience, and become part of the growing SSbD community. It is a two full and two half-day event with a highly engaging and interactive programme including presentations by experts and hands-on training on the PARC SSbD toolbox.
Tentative Contents	The programme will focus on the in depth understanding of the SSbD framework and the stage gate innovation process, demonstrating real-life applications, followed by hands on training for the participants on the PARC SSbD toolbox. In the breakout sessions participants will work in small groups in the application of case studies using the PARC SSbD toolbox and get familiar with its functionalities. In the last day, presentation by the groups on their learnings and their user experience will be presented and discussed.
Learning outcomes	The participants will learn how to apply in practice the concepts and assessment methods described in the SSbD framework (i.e. hazard assessment, exposure assessment, risk assessment, environmental sustainability assessment, and social and economic sustainability assessment) with various levels of data availability (data poor and data rich chemicals, "dry-run" with minimal available data), representing the various stages of innovation in the development phase of chemicals and materials.
Target audience	Researchers, industry, SMEs, students
Duration	2 full and 2 half-days
Difficulty level	Intermediate
Pre-requisites /Requirements	Basic concepts of exposure and hazard assessment, LCA, SSbD framework
Selection process	Applications will be evaluated by field experts and decisions on successful applicants will be announced via email by mid July 2024.
Maximum number of participants	60
Scientific coordinator & contacts	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, AUTH Denis Sarigiannis (sarigiannis@auth.gr) Spyros Karakitsios (spyros.karakitsios@gmail.com)
Dates and location	22-25 October, 2024 Thessaloniki, Greece, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, AUTH

This meeting is part of the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals. This partnership has received funding from the European Union.

SSBD BOOT CAMP

2024-10-22
DOC. VERSION 02

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

PARC SSbD boot camp

Course Programme

This partnership has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101057014.

Course Details

Title	PARC SSbD Bootcamp
Date	Tuesday 22 October 2024 - Friday 25 October 2024
Time	Tuesday 22 October 2024, 13:30 - Friday 25 October 2024, 14:30 (EEST)
Venue	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki KEDEA Building, Tritis Septemvriou, 54636, Thessaloniki, Greece
Scientific Coordinators	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, AUTH Denis Sarigiannis (sarigiannis@auth.gr) Spyros Karakitsios (spyros.karakitsios@gmail.com)

Programme

Day 1: Tuesday, 22/10

Time	Topic	Speakers	Activity type
13:30 – 14:30 ⁽⁶⁰⁾	Light Lunch		
14:30 – 14:45 ⁽¹⁵⁾	Welcome, aims and scope of the meeting	Spyros Karakitsios, AUTH	
14:45 – 15:45 ⁽⁶⁰⁾	Merging the SSbD framework with the innovation stage approach/ SSbD policy context/ Integration of innovation stage-gate approach in SSbD	Jaco Westra, RIVM/ Garbine Guiu, DG-RTD, Aleksandra Malyska, DG ENV/ Fotini Nikiforou, AUTH	Lecture
15:45 – 16:15 ⁽³⁰⁾	Coffee-Break		
16:15 – 17:00 ⁽⁴⁵⁾	Key points of the JRC SSbD methodological guidance	Irantzu Garmendia Aguirre, JRC)	Lecture
17:00 – 17:30 ⁽³⁰⁾	Perspective of industrial stakeholders in the SSbD thinking	Eva-Kathrin Schillinger, CEFIC	Lecture
17:30 – 18:30 ⁽⁶⁰⁾	Debate on the SSbD concept and implementation	Chair: Jaco Westra, RIVM; Participants: AUTH, EMPA, JRC, RTD, CEFIC	Lecture

Day 2: Wednesday, 22/10

Time	Topic	Speakers	Activity type
09:00 – 09:10 (10')	Welcome and agenda of 2nd day	Spyros Karakitsios, AUTH	
09:10 – 10:30 (80')	Introduction to the PARC SSbD toolbox (presentation of the toolbox environment)	Fotini Nikiforou, Karolos Lykos, Spyros Karakitsios, AUTH	Theory
10:30 – 11:00 (30')	Coffee-Break		
11:00 – 11:15 (15')	The bisphenols and alternatives case study – Concept	Spyros Karakitsios, AUTH	Case study demonstration
11:15 – 12:30 (60')	The bisphenols and alternatives case study – Step 1 (demonstration)	Gianluca Selvestrel, IRFMN; Joanke Van Dijk, EMPA; Ziyue Zheng, IVL	Case study demonstration
12:30 – 13:30 (60')	Light lunch		
13:30 – 14:30 (60')	The bisphenols and alternatives case study – Step 2 (demonstration)	Fotini Nikiforou, AUTH; Tomas Rydberg IVL	Case study demonstration
14:30 – 16:00 (90')	Break-out groups – hands-on application on the case study – Step 1	Gianluca Selvestrel, IRFMN; Joanke Van Dijk, EMPA; Ziyue Zheng, IVL	Hands—on exercise
16:00 – 16:30 (30')	Coffee break		
16:30 – 18:00 (75')	Break-out groups – hands-on application on the case study – Step 2	Fotini Nikiforou, AUTH; Rosella Telaretti, IVL; Tomas Rydberg, IVL	Hands—on exercise
18:00 – 18:30 (30')	Q&A regarding the implementation of the case study regarding Step 1 and Step 2	Spyros Karakitsios, AUTH	

Day 3: Thursday, 24/10

Time	Topic	Speakers	Activity type
09:00 – 09:20 (20')	Welcome and agenda of 3rd day	Spyros Karakitsios, AUTH	
09:20 – 11:00 (100')	The bisphenols and alternatives case study – Step 3	Fotini Nikiforou, AUTH)	Case study demonstration
11:00 – 11:30 (30')	Coffee-Break		
11:30 – 13:00 (90')	Break-out groups – hands-on application on the case study – Step 3	Fotini Nikiforou, Achilleas, Karakoltzidis, AUTH	Hands-on exercise
13:00 – 14:00 (60')	Light lunch		
14:00 – 15:30 (90')	The bisphenols and alternatives case study – Step 4	Rosella Telaretti, Tomas Rydberg, IVL	Case study demonstration
15:30 – 15:45 (15')	Coffee break		
15:45 – 17:30 (90')	Break-out groups – hands-on application on the case study – Step 4	Rosella Telaretti, Tomas, Rydberg, IVL	Hands-on exercise
17:30 – 18:00 (25')	Break-out groups – hands-on application on the case study – Integration of results and scoring system	Fotini Nikiforou, Achilleas Karakoltzidis, AUTH	Hands-on exercise
18:00 – 18:30 (30')	Break-out groups – Collation of conclusions from applying the SSbD framework in the various steps		Hands-on exercise

Day 4: Friday, 25/10

Time	Topic	Speakers	Activity type
09:00 – 09:10 (10')	Presentation and discussion of breakout groups 1 and 2 – Experiences from Step 1		Discussion
09:10 – 09:20 (10')	Discussion on experiences from Step 1		Discussion
09:20 – 09:30 (10')	Presentation and discussion of breakout groups 3 and 4 – Experiences from Step 2		Discussion
09:30 – 09:40 (10')	Discussion on experiences from Step 2		Discussion
09:40 – 09:50 (10')	Presentation and discussion of breakout groups 5 and 6 – Experiences from Step 3		Discussion
09:50 – 10:00 (10')	Discussion on experiences from Step 3		Discussion
10:00 – 10:10 (10')	Presentation and discussion of breakout groups 7 and 8 – Experiences from Step 4		Discussion
10:10 – 10:20 (10')	Discussion on experiences from Step 4		Discussion
10:20 – 11:00 (40')	Break-out groups – hands-on application on the case study – Integration of results and scoring system		Hands-on exercise
11:00 – 11:30 (30')	Coffee break		
11:30 – 12:30 (30')	Overview of elements needed for the further operationalisation of SSbD and work on the toolbox/ Improved scoping of the problem/ Safety assessment and the use of NAMs/ Improved integration of safety and sustainability assessment at early innovation stages	Bernd Nowack, EMPA/ Jaco Westra, RIVM, Bernd Nowack, EMPA/ Kiara Aiello-Holden, BfR/Tomas Rydberg,IVL	Lecture
12:50 – 13:10 (30')	Next steps of development of the PARC SSbD toolbox	Fotini Nikiforou, Karolos Lykos, AUTH	Lecture

Time	Topic	Speakers	Activity type
13:10 – 13:30 (30')	Close and looking ahead	Denis Sarigiannis, AUTH	
13:30 – 14:30 (60')	Light Lunch		

This course is part of the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals.
This partnership has received funding from the European Union.

Training Evaluation Survey Results

Second SSbD Bootcamp

22-25.10.2024

METHODOLOGY

For the reporting on trainees' satisfaction, we gathered feedback on five primary categories: satisfaction with course organisation, course content/structure, delivery methods and trainers, satisfaction with exercises, tools, and overall satisfaction. These categories were assessed through a survey, where respondents rated their level of agreement on a Likert scale, ranging from "1. Strongly disagree" to "5. Strongly agree" in the first four sections. In the assessment of the overall satisfaction, the Likert scale varied from "1. Very dissatisfied" to "5. Very satisfied."

Below, an overview of the aggregated data collected from the satisfaction survey is presented for each of the five categories. Strengths of the training and also areas for improvement are also highlighted to further optimise future sessions. Where applicable, qualitative feedback from participants has been included to provide context and enhance understanding of the numerical data.

RESULTS

I. Overall Satisfaction

Key Additional Comments: Do you have any suggestions on how to improve this course?

- Additional time for discussion and guidance.
- Materials and tools prior to the start of the program.
- Greater emphasis on tools and results use in real-world contexts.

II. Detailed Satisfaction

Strong Points:

Course Organization: High levels of satisfaction, specifically, 52% of participants strongly agreed that the venue and logistical arrangements met expectations, and 43% felt similarly about the timeliness of information and materials delivery. These results reflect efficient planning and coordination.

Course Delivery and Trainers: Participants responded positively to the course structure and delivery. Over 50% strongly agreed that the course objectives were clearly defined, and 43% believed the methods of delivery were appropriate. Additionally, trainer interaction was a standout feature, with 66% of participants strongly agreeing that trainers encouraged active participation.

Trainer Performance and Feedback: The trainers received particularly high marks for their ability to facilitate discussions, with 66% of respondents strongly agreeing that ample opportunities for questions and feedback were provided.

Points for Improvement

Course Content and Balance: Although satisfaction with course content was generally high, 34% of respondents felt neutral about whether the course introduced new information. Similarly, the balance between presentations and activities could be improved, with 26% indicating neutrality and 20% disagreeing that the balance was optimal.

Exercises: Opinions on exercises showed room for improvement. While 48% strongly agreed they were able to perform the exercises, 43% expressed neutrality regarding the time allocated for these tasks. Additionally, 26% of participants were neutral about overall satisfaction with the exercises, suggesting a potential need for better alignment with expectations.

Tool Usability: Feedback on the tools used during the course indicated mixed satisfaction. Although many found the tools useful for exercises, 20% of respondents neither agreed nor disagreed on their ease of application, highlighting an opportunity to enhance usability and clarity of instructions.

A. Satisfaction with course organisation

Key Additional Comments:

- Group activities in round tables and a trainer for each group.
- Support for tool installation.
- Participants expected to receive the presentations.

B. Satisfaction with course content/structure, delivery methods and trainers

Key Additional Comments:

- Better alignment of theoretical and practical sessions.
- Challenging content for non-experts.

C. Satisfaction with exercises

Key Additional Comments:

- Clearer instructions.

III. Input on Additional Training Needs

- Potential applications of SSBD thinking approaches in industry and SMEs

Annex 5.

Training Videos on PARCopedia YouTube Channel

Aim of this SOP

- Guarantee that all the relevant study results are communicated to all study participants (workers and equally to controls) and national and EU stakeholders.
- The CP describes the different target audiences, the objectives/actions desired, the message content for each stakeholder/group, the method of choice to convey the message and, finally, the best moment in time for the message to be communicated.
- Stakeholder, group/Objectives/Data to be communicated/Delivery methods, venue/When

data to be communicated, delivery methods, venue/When

Training for PARC Waste Management Survey

PARCopedia

Playlist • 12 videos • 110 views

To ask any questions you may have on this recording go to: <https://survey-insa.min-saude.pt/redcap/survey...more>

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